

Table for Lay Public Dissemination

Acronym	GNOSTIC
Name of user	Marek Kraft, Przemyslaw Aszkowski, Bartosz Ptak, Dominik Pieczynski
Title	Graph neural networks for camera network spatial topology discovery and activity control
Objectives (Max 150 words, Calibri 11)	<p>The objective is to research and develop a collaborative method for activity control of a multi-device camera system using Graph Neural Networks (GNN). The method will enable automatic tuning of the system's parameters based on objects (e.g. humans, cars, etc.) re-identified between cameras.</p> <p>The ultimate aim of the research is to determine if it is possible to use Convolution Neural Networks and Graph Neural Networks to build an algorithm that estimates the real-world, spatial topology network of the camera system. This information in turn can be used to control the activity of individual cameras and the whole network, as well as extension of existing methods for multi-camera surveillance involving tracking, re-identification, activity recognition etc.</p>
Impact (Max 150 words, Calibri 11)	<p>Automatic tuning of the system parameters based on object re-identification is an important research issue, especially in the case of large system deployment or extension of existing systems with new devices. The application of Graph Neural Networks to better control the multi-camera system with the spatial topology of the system should allow for improving the re-identification of people moving between cameras, with improved accuracy in comparison to bare re-identification without spatial topology knowledge.</p> <p>As part of the work publication of the gathered dataset (from a large-scale multi-camera video surveillance system) with anonymized people identification within cameras is planned.</p>